

MEASUREMENT OF LIGHT POLLUTION IN THE GRANA VALLEY

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Abstract

The Valle Grana is a valley in the province of Cuneo, Piedmont, northern Italy. It takes its name from the Grana stream, a tributary of the Maira river which flows through the valley. The territory of the municipality of Castelmagno, set in the upper Grana valley, is part of a unique alpine landscape characterized by an uncontaminated starry sky. The measurements of the sky brightness, made in the years 2020-2021 from two different locations, allow to estimate the light pollution in the higher portion of this valley, normally to a Bortle Scale 3 typical of a "Rural Sky" that occasionally decreases to Bortle Scale 2, a "Typical Truly Dark Site".

Introduction: measuring the brightness of the night sky

Among the several types of light pollution, the most disturbing for astronomical observations is the artificial sky glow, which is connected to the scattering of artificial ground light in the atmosphere. This component of pollution mainly affects the surroundings of cities, which are the sources of light pollution.

To measure the light pollution effects, the Bortle scale of night sky brightness was introduced 20 years ago by the American amateur astronomer, John E. Bortle, in an article published in popular magazine *Sky and Telescope* (Bortle 2001). It uses a nine-point scale to characterize the quality of the night sky. Bortle recognized the Naked Eye Limiting Magnitude (NELM) of categorizing sky brightness. His scale suggests that for a Class 1 'excellent' site, the limiting magnitude should be '7.6–8.0 mag in V and for Class 2, a 'typical truly dark site' 7.1–7.5 mag in V. However, he ascribed approximate limiting magnitudes to each class on his scale; they ranged from mag V = 7.6 to 8.0 for class 1 and magnitude 4.0 or less for the most light-polluted inner-city skies (Bortle class 9). For many observers these faint magnitude limits are unrealistically faint, and few people have the visual acuity to detect eighth magnitude (or even seventh magnitude) even in the darkest of locations. Certainly such faint stars would require exceptional eyesight, a fully dark adapted eye of a younger person, and experience in using averted scotopic vision.

On the other hand, it has always been noted that the traditional naked-eye magnitude limit of 6 is merely approximate. As has been reported by Harold F. Weaver in his review "The visibility of the stars without optical aid" (Weaver 1947):

«The faintest stars in Ptolemy's Almagest, for example, are of magnitude 5.4. Those in al Sufi's catalog are of magnitude 5.6. The more modern catalogs have somewhat fainter limits.

The faintest stars in Argelander's Uranometria Nova are on the average of magnitude 5.7, and those in the Atlas Coelisticus Novus of Heis (who was noted for his keen eyesight) are of 6.1. Houzeau, in his Uranométrie Générale, has recorded stars of magnitude 6.4 and Gould, who many times remarked about the exceptionally clear atmosphere at Córdoba, states that persons of ordinarily good vision could see stars of the seventh magnitude. »

In the scientific literature (Crume 2014), as in the popular astronomy, we can find evidence of observations of stars in some occasions even to 8th magnitude with the naked eye. Apart from unusual acuity or special observing techniques, such high limits may in many cases be explained by scintillation, with momentary glimpses being taken as the typical threshold. From this point of view, the Bortle scale does not make estimating sky quality and darkness any easier, as it only ascribes an arbitrary class number to a given site and set of observing conditions. Determination of the Bortle class relies partly on the limiting magnitude of stars, though it also is based partly on the visibility of faint natural sources of light such as the zodiacal light, Gegenschein, airglow and on diffuse celestial objects. In the final analysis, the Bortle class is a subjective qualitative estimate of a given observer and location, and is not a quantitative objective measurement. A more quantitative way of expressing night sky brightness is to use physical units for surface brightness, given that the night sky can be considered as a hemispherical surface with the observer at the centre.

One popular unit of night sky brightness is magnitudes per square arc second (mag arcsec⁻²). First consider a star of magnitude V = 22, which is more than a million times fainter than a naked eye star of magnitude 7 observed at an excellent location. Although stars are essentially point sources of light, we can imagine that light being spread over a tiny square in the sky, whose side in angular measure is 1 square arcsecond (there are 3600 square arcseconds in a square degree). A hemisphere comprises 2.7×10^{11} square arcsec, so 1 square arcsecond is a very tiny area of the sky. The surface brightness of the night sky, denoted as S, is

given in the commonly used astronomical units of magnitudes per square arcsecond (mag arcsec^{-2}). It is a derivative of the magnitude scale defining the visual impact of the star's brightness as a point light source. Magnitude scale is a logarithmic, relative and reverse scale, in which a star of magnitude 0 is 100 times brighter than a star of magnitude 5. The mag arcsec^{-2} scale determines the surface brightness of diffuse astronomical objects, such as nebulae, galaxies, comets, or just a background sky. So, we assume $22.0 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ as the typical brightness of the night sky background during minimum solar activity, excluding stars brighter than magnitude 7, away from the Milky Way and from Gegenschein and zodiacal light (Falchi 2016). The darkest possible skies are at about $22 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$, and this figure represents a typical value of the natural airglow which is always present, though somewhat variable in direction and in time. A sky which is 20 times brighter than this natural airglow background would be at about $18.75 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ and this would be a typical value in many urban environments.

If the sky is 60 times brighter than the natural airglow background, then the brightness would be $17.5 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$, a value found in the central areas of the world's large cities with Bortle class 8. For example, the value of zenithal sky brightness in Turin the major city in Piedmont is $17.7 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ (<https://www.lightpollutionmap.info/>). Of course the units of mag arcsec^{-2} are an inverse logarithmic scale, and therefore not very intuitive for non-astronomers unused to dealing in stellar magnitudes.

Fig.1 – Grana Valley, and the location of Rifugio Fauniera ($44^{\circ} 23' 41'' \text{ N} - 7^{\circ} 07' 36'' \text{ E} - 2.305 \text{ m s.l.m.}$) and San Magno Sanctuary, ($44^{\circ} 24' 2.48'' \text{ N}, 7^{\circ} 10' 15.38'' \text{ E} - 1761 \text{ m s.l.m.}$) in the Castelmagno municipality.

Materials and methods

To measure the zenithal sky brightness in the Grana Valley in the municipality of Castelmagno, we used a “Sky Quality Meter - L” (SQM) produced by Unihedron (<http://www.unihedron.com/projects/sqm-l/>). This Sky Quality Meter is a fine and interesting night sky brightness photometer. Its low cost and pocket size allow members of the general public to quantify the quality of the night sky.

The SQM measures luminance (surface brightness) for a patch of the sky, in units of magnitudes per square arc second (mag/arcsec^2). The photosensitive element of the meter is a silicon photodiode (TAOS TSL237S light-to-frequency converter), which responds to light with wavelengths in the range of 320 to 1050 nm, with a peak at about 680 nm. The photodiode is covered by a HOYA CM-500 filter, which reduces the wavelength response to 320 to 720 nm, in order to provide better agreement with the wavelength response of human night vision. The response of the TSL237S has a small, stable, temperature dependence, so the SQM contains an internal temperature sensor which is used by the SQM software to provide compensation (i.e. the results reported by the SQM should have no temperature dependence over the range -25 to 70 degrees Celsius).

In order to understand the SQM measurements, we consider first the patch of the sky, or the solid angle, over which the measurement is made. The receiving angle of the instrument is about $\sim 20^{\circ}$; the sensitivity to a point source $\sim 19^{\circ}$ off-axis is a factor of 10 lower than on-axis. A point source $\sim 20^{\circ}$ and $\sim 40^{\circ}$ off-axis would register 3.0 and 5.0 magnitudes fainter, respectively.

Second we consider its accuracy. That is, on the second digit of the display ($\pm 0.01 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$), but we must take into account also the spectral response. The conversion factors for the polluted sky to the natural sky appear to be critical. The conversion factor for the polluted sky differs from the conversion factor for the natural sky by less than $\pm 0.05 \text{ mag arcsec}^{-2}$ and can be related to the sky brightness in V and its B-V color

index, as explained by Cinzano (2005). For this reason, we assume ± 0.05 mag arcsec⁻² for the instrumental error. Instead Kyba et al (2011) estimates a ± 0.1 mag arcsec⁻² for the instrumental error.

Year-Month	San Magno (mag arcsec ⁻²)	Fauniera (mag arcsec ⁻²)	New Moon period
2019 July	21.77±0.05	21.89±0.05	from 01 to 07
2019 August	21.75±0.05	21.70±0.05	from 01 to 04
2019 September	21.80±0.05	21.90±0.05	from 25 to 30
2019 October	21.77±0.05	not available	from 25 to 31
2019 November	21.86±0.05	not available	from 23 al 28
2019 December	21.91±0.05	not available	from 23 to 28
2020 January	21.75±0.05	not available	from 21 to 27
2020 February	COVID19 LOCK_DOWN		
2020 March			
2020 April			
2020 May			
2020 June			
2020 July	21.70±0.05	21.66±0.05	from 18 to 22

Table 1 – Sky glow measurements from San Magno Sanctuary and Fauniera refuge, two different locations in the valley: San Magno Sanctuary (44° 24' 2.48" N, 7° 10' 15.38" E - 1761 m s.l.m.) and Fauniera Refuge (44° 23' 41" N – 7° 07' 36" E– 2.305 m s.l.m.).

Every measure consists in the best value of the sky glow, measured on a clear sky during the period without the Moon, as shown in table 1.

During late autumn and winter, the roads to the Fauniera Refuge is icy or snowy, the Fauniera's pass road is closed as well as the refuge. For this reason during the months between October-January the measurements from that location are not available. Instead in the period between February-May 2020, the valley was not accessible due to the SARS COVID2 lock down in that period.

Fig.2
– Sky glow

values in the period between July 2019 and July 2020

ANALISYS

We obtain a value of 21.79 ± 0.08 mag arcsec⁻² (about 0.17 mcd m⁻²), as a yearly mean estimate of the sky glow in the Castelmagno municipality, which corresponds to Bortle Class 3 “Rural Sky”. The naked-eye limiting magnitude, recorded as 6.7 mag, confirm this class. As shown in figure 2, three measurements are

equal or superior to the Bortle Class 2 threshold and if we considering the error bar about 35% of the sky glow observations fall in the Bortle Class 2 threshold. This means that, occasionally, the sky glow decreases to Bortle Scale 2, identified as a "Typical Truly Dark Site".

Also, considering the standard deviation, our measurements are better than the values of zenith sky brightness values (2015) reported by <https://www.lightpollutionmap.info/> site, for the geographical coordinates of San Magno Sanctuary (44.40069, 7.1709) SQM value of 21.65 mag arcsec⁻² and 21.69 mag arcsec⁻² for Fauniera Refuge (44.39472, 7.12666).

CONCLUSIONS

From Fauniera refuge, the light pollution is visible along the horizon in Cuneo's direction (Po Valley). Clouds may appear faintly illuminated in the brightest parts of the sky near the horizon but are dark overhead. The Milky Way appears complex, and many globular clusters are distinguishable at naked-eye. M33 is easy to see with averted vision. The naked-eye limiting magnitude is recorded at 6.7 mag, making it a typical Rural Dark Sky. As shown, our measurements with a yearly mean value of the sky glow of 21.79 ± 0.08 mag arcsec⁻² fully confirm a Bortle Class 3 as a typical of "Rural Sky". But at the same time they show that, occasionally, the sky glow decrease at Bortle Scale 2 "Typical Truly Dark Site". This is an exceptional starry sky for a place like Castelmagno in Val Grana that is at less than 100 kilometers away from a large city like Turin.

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